

THE ROLE OF CONTEXT IN THE PROCESS OF TEACHING FOREIGN LANGUAGE VOCABULARY

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19160743>

Abstract:

The development of vocabulary knowledge is a crucial aspect of foreign language learning, as lexical competence forms the basis of effective communication. This study examined the role of context in the teaching of foreign language vocabulary and how contextualized instruction contributes to deeper comprehension and improved retention. The study applied a mixed-methods approach, combining both qualitative and quantitative research methods. The results indicate that presenting vocabulary in meaningful contexts significantly improves learners' comprehension, retention, and appropriate use of lexical items in real communication.

Keywords: vocabulary acquisition, context, foreign language teaching, communicative competence, contextualized instruction.

Introduction

Vocabulary is regarded as one of the most crucial aspects of language instruction. (Yeganehpour, 2021). Building a rich vocabulary in a second language (L2) is essential to gain a sufficient level of L2 proficiency and, therefore, entails a large part of L2 education (EVELIEN MULDER, 2018). Therefore, teaching vocabulary effectively is a key factor in foreign language education.

In the past, the main language teaching methodology from the beginning of the nineteenth century was Grammar-Translation. A lesson would typically have one or two new grammar rules, a list of vocabulary items and some practice examples to translate from L1 into L2 or vice versa (Schmitt, 2020). However, this method does not always help to students remember words for a long time or use them correctly in real situations.

Nowadays, modern teaching approaches indicate that vocabulary is learned better when it is presented in context. Context plays an important part in restricting the meaning of words in sentences or passages (Li, 2022). Words have meaning only when they are used in sentences, situations and real communication and context helps students understand meaning, see how words are used together and remember them more easily. This research studies how contextual teaching improves understanding, memory, and correct usage of new words.

The aim of this study is to examine how contextualized instruction improves student's vocabulary understanding, retention and correct usage of new words and it highlights the effectiveness of this research, the impact of lexical interference on word learning and the importance of adapting teaching methods to L1 learners' need.

The scientific novelty of this study lies in analysing specific lexical interference between Uzbek and English languages in vocabulary learning and applying context-based vocabulary teaching method, including professional communication contexts, for Uzbek undergraduate EFL (English as a foreign language) learners.

Methodology

Research Design

This study used a mixed-method research design, combining both quantitative and qualitative approaches.

Participants

The research was conducted with 40 undergraduate students studying English as a foreign language. They were divided into two groups:

- Experimental group (20 students) – received vocabulary through contextual teaching methods.
- Control group (20 students) – received traditional vocabulary instruction based on word lists and translation.

Both groups were at approximately the same language proficiency level.

To collect data, the following instruments were used:

1. Pre-test and Post-test: Measured understanding of meanings and ability to use words in sentences.

2. Classroom Observation: To observe student engagement.

3. Student Questionnaire: To gather opinions about contextual learning.

Data Analysis

Quantitative data from the tests were analysed using descriptive statistics, which included average scores and percentage variations between pre-test and post-test outcomes.

Qualitative data from observations and surveys were analysed to identify patterns in student involvement, motivation and perceived value of contextual learning.

Results and Outcomes

The study found that students who learned vocabulary through contextual teaching showed higher improvement in vocabulary test scores compared to students who learned through traditional methods. Contextual instruction helped students better understand word meanings, use vocabulary correctly in sentences, and remember new words for a longer time. Additionally, contextual learning activities increased student motivation, confidence, and classroom participation during language learning tasks.

Conclusion

In conclusion, this study demonstrated that contextual vocabulary teaching is more effective than traditional memorization-based methods. Context helped learners connect meaning with real communication situations, which improved their vocabulary acquisition. Therefore, context-based instruction is recommended for improving vocabulary learning outcomes in foreign language teaching.

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